

TABLE II.

Absorption maxima of the acridcins and analogous dycstuffs.

Name.	-phthalein.	-quinolinein.	-cinchome- ronein.	-quinoline 1 :2 :3- tricarboxylein.	-acridien.
Phenol-	5540Å	5560Å	5520Å	5560Å	5880Å
Resorcinol-	4940	4950	4950	4930	5000
Phloroglucinol-	4980	4990	4980	4930	5055
<i>m</i> -Diethylami- nophenol-	5510	5540	5540	5540	5930
Tetrabromo- resorcinol-	5250	5250	5250	5180	5460

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A New Volumetric Method for the Estimation of Lead.

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Various methods have been proposed by different investigators for estimating lead volumetrically, the dichromate method being perhaps the most convenient. The object of the present paper is to describe a very simple and ready method for the estimation of lead volumetrically, in the absence of other metallic ions. It was found that neutral solutions of lead can be titrated with standard potassium sulphate solution, the end-point being determined by the use of fluorescein as an external indicator. In the concentrated solutions the end-point is quite sharp, the indicator (greenish-yellow) becoming vermilion-red in presence of Pb-ions. In dilute solutions the change in the colour of the indicator is not so sharp. With the decrease of the concentration of Pb-ions, the red colour gradually fades to a distinct yellow, which persists so long as Pb-ions are present.

Acid solutions of lead should be evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the slight hydrolysis which might take place will not affect the result, as the solubility product of lead sulphate is much below that of the basic salt formed. The acid solutions cannot be

neutralised with ammonia as the presence of ammonium salts was found to affect the colour reaction with fluorescein. The evaporated solid is next extracted with minimum quantity of water (preferably 30 to 40 c.c.) and transferred to a conical flask. 5-10 C.c. of rectified spirit are added to the solution, which is then titrated with standard potassium sulphate solution. Small drops of the indicator (0.2% solution of sodium fluoresceinate in water) are placed on a white glazed porcelain tile and drops from the solution of lead are brought and touched with the indicator, the end-point being obtained when there is no change in the colouration of the indicator. A blank experiment may with advantage be performed by touching a similar droplet of the indicator with a drop of water for the final comparison.

This method also appears suitable for the estimation of sulphate by adding to the solution of the sulphate an excess of a standard solution of lead and titrating the excess of lead with standard potassium sulphate.

The yellow colour which gives the indication of the presence of lead persists so long as there is 0.03 to 0.02 mg. of lead per c.c. In spite of the limited applicability of the method, the results obtained with fairly concentrated solutions (1 to 3%) of lead, is quite satisfactory. The results are given in the following table.

Approx. conc. of soln.	Wt. of the Pb as found in a given vol. by direct estimation as PbSO ₄ .	Wt. of Pb as PbSO ₄ in the same vol. by the given method.	% Error.
0.50 N	1.9790	1.9850	+0.30
0.35	1.0220	1.0180	-0.39
0.20	0.6292	0.6320	+0.44
0.15	0.5134	0.5108	-0.50
0.10	0.3954	0.3965	+0.30
0.075	0.2570	0.2556	-0.54
0.05	0.1985	0.1976	-0.46

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